

**Supplementary Information for
Inelastic Electron Tunneling through Adatoms and
Molecular Nanomagnets**

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S1 Summary of notation

Numbers of sections, figures, tables, equations and references in this supplemental material are prefixed with letter “S”. Numbers without prefix refer to the figures and equations from the main article.

ϵ one-particle energies ϵ_F Fermi energy of the surface E many-body energies of the nanosystem, tip and surface \mathcal{E} energies of the whole system i index of the magnetic center in the nanosystem m, n, M magnetic quantum number σ spin quantum number	Γ label of the irreducible representation at a magnetic center μ label of a component of Γ if it is multidimensional; $\mu \equiv m\sigma$ for a spherically symmetric site without spin-orbit coupling k a star of a wave vector combined with the band index for the conduction states in tip and surface
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\hat{d}^\dagger, \hat{d} creation and annihilation operators at magnetic centers in the nanosystem	$ v\rangle$ intermediate virtual states of the tunneling process
\hat{a}^\dagger, \hat{a} creation and annihilation operators in the tip	$ f\rangle$ final states of the tunneling process
\hat{b}^\dagger, \hat{b} creation and annihilation operators in the surface	$\hat{\mathcal{H}}$ Hamiltonian and its parts
N ground-state number of electrons in the nanosystem	$\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ tunneling operator (tip/surface \leftrightarrow nanosystem)
$ \psi\rangle$ many-body eigenstates of the nanosystem	$\hat{\mathcal{T}}$ hopping operator connecting individual magnetic centers in the nanosystem
α, β, γ labels of the eigenstates $ \psi\rangle$ for a given filling N of the nanosystem	$\hat{\mathcal{O}}$ operator giving amplitudes of inelastic transitions in the nanosystem induced by an electron tunneling through it
V tip–surface bias voltage	A tip \leftrightarrow nanosystem tunneling amplitude
$ \phi_s\rangle$ ground state of the surface, one-particle levels filled up to ϵ_F	B surface \leftrightarrow nanosystem tunneling amplitude
$ \phi_t\rangle$ ground state of the tip, one-particle levels filled up to the energy $\epsilon_F + eV$	t amplitude of hopping between individual centers
E_s energy of the state $ \phi_s\rangle$	S, L, J spin, orbital and total moment of a magnetic center
E_t energy of the state $ \phi_t\rangle$	g differential conductance
$ \chi\rangle$ states of the whole system in the form of a direct product $ \phi_t\rangle \otimes \phi_s\rangle \otimes \psi\rangle$	ρ density of states in the tip and surface

S2 Derivation of the differential conductance

We are concerned with arrangements composed of two electrodes (STM tip and the surface) and a magnetic nanosystem placed in between the electrodes. The electrodes are assumed to host non-interacting electrons, the nanosystem is a general many-body system.

The contribution to the tunneling current from processes that start when the magnetic nanosystem resides in an N -electron state $|\psi_{N\alpha}\rangle$ is given by the

Figure S1: Two contributions to the positive current I_+ : an electron tunnels from the tip to the surface (top path) and a hole tunnels from the surface to the tip (bottom path).

Kramers–Heisenberg formula

$$I_{\pm}^{(\alpha)} = \pm \frac{2\pi e}{\hbar} \sum_{f_{\pm}} \left| \sum_v \frac{\langle f_{\pm} | \hat{\mathcal{V}} | v \rangle \langle v | \hat{\mathcal{V}} | \chi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{\mathcal{E}_v - \mathcal{E}_{N\alpha}} \right|^2 \delta(\mathcal{E}_{f_{\pm}} - \mathcal{E}_{N\alpha}), \quad (2)$$

where the positive current I_+ comes from the final states

$$|f_+\rangle = \hat{b}_{k'\nu\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger \hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu} |\chi_{N\beta}\rangle \quad \text{with} \quad \epsilon_k < \epsilon_F + eV \quad \text{and} \quad \epsilon_{k'} > \epsilon_F, \quad (S1a)$$

and the negative current I_- from the final states

$$|f_-\rangle = \hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \hat{b}_{k'\nu\Gamma'\mu'} |\chi_{N\beta}\rangle \quad \text{with} \quad \epsilon_k > \epsilon_F + eV \quad \text{and} \quad \epsilon_{k'} < \epsilon_F. \quad (S1b)$$

The final states are written with the help of product states $|\chi_{N\beta}\rangle = |\phi_t\rangle \otimes |\phi_s\rangle \otimes |\psi_{N\beta}\rangle$, where $|\phi_t\rangle$ and $|\phi_s\rangle$ are ground states of the tip and surface electrodes (each of which is a Fermi sea filled up to the corresponding Fermi level). The final-state energies then are

$$\mathcal{E}_{f_+} = E_{N\beta} + E_t + E_s - \epsilon_k + \epsilon_{k'}, \quad (S2a)$$

$$\mathcal{E}_{f_-} = E_{N\beta} + E_t + E_s + \epsilon_k - \epsilon_{k'}, \quad (S2b)$$

where $E_{N\beta}$, E_t and E_s are energies of $|\psi_{N\beta}\rangle$, $|\phi_t\rangle$ and $|\phi_s\rangle$. As discussed in the main text, the tunneling Hamiltonian $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ has the form

$$\hat{\mathcal{V}} = \sum_{ki\Gamma\mu} \left(A_{ki\Gamma} \hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} + A_{ki\Gamma}^* \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu} + B_{ki\Gamma} \hat{b}_{ki\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} + B_{ki\Gamma}^* \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \hat{b}_{ki\Gamma\mu} \right), \quad (1)$$

which implies that each final state can be reached by two paths, that is, via two intermediate states: one with $N + 1$ electrons and the other with $N - 1$ electrons in

Table S1: Combinations of intermediate and final states that give non-vanishing contributions in the Kramers–Heisenberg formula, Eq. (2). The restrictions on k and k' that apply to the intermediate states are the same as the restrictions that apply to the corresponding final states and that are listed in Eqs. (S1).

final state	intermediate state $ v\rangle$	intermediate energy \mathcal{E}_v
$ f_+\rangle = \hat{b}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger \hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu} \chi_{N\beta}\rangle$	$\hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu} \chi_{N+1,\gamma}\rangle$	$E_{N+1,\gamma} + E_t + E_s - \epsilon_k$
	$\hat{b}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu}^\dagger \chi_{N-1,\gamma}\rangle$	$E_{N-1,\gamma} + E_t + E_s + \epsilon_{k'}$
$ f_-\rangle = \hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \hat{b}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu'} \chi_{N\beta}\rangle$	$\hat{b}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu'\sigma'} \chi_{N+1,\gamma}\rangle$	$E_{N+1,\gamma} + E_t + E_s - \epsilon_{k'}$
	$\hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \chi_{N-1,\gamma}\rangle$	$E_{N-1,\gamma} + E_t + E_s + \epsilon_k$

the nanosystem (see Fig. S1). The combinations of the intermediate states $|v\rangle$ and the final states $|f_\pm\rangle$ that contribute to the Kramers–Heisenberg formula, Eq. (2), are summarized in Table S1. We will work out the partial expressions corresponding to the individual rows of the table separately.

S2.1 Positive current

The first half of the sum over the intermediate states $|v\rangle$, which involves the intermediate states with an extra electron in the nanosystem, can be consecutively rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_v^{(1)} \frac{\langle f_+ | \hat{\mathcal{V}} | v \rangle \langle v | \hat{\mathcal{V}} | \chi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{\mathcal{E}_v - \mathcal{E}_{N\alpha}} &= \\
\sum_\gamma \frac{\langle \chi_{N\beta} | \hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \hat{b}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu'} \hat{\mathcal{V}} \hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu} | \chi_{N+1,\gamma} \rangle \langle \chi_{N+1,\gamma} | \hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \hat{\mathcal{V}} | \chi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{E_{N+1,\gamma} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon_k} &= \\
B_{k'i'\Gamma'} A_{ki\Gamma}^* \sum_\gamma \frac{\langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} | \psi_{N+1,\gamma} \rangle \langle \psi_{N+1,\gamma} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{E_{N+1,\gamma} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon_k} &= \\
B_{k'i'\Gamma'} A_{ki\Gamma}^* \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon_k} \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle. & \quad (\text{S3})
\end{aligned}$$

In the first step, we substituted the appropriate expressions for $|f_+\rangle$, $|v\rangle$ and \mathcal{E}_v . In the second step, we inserted the tunneling operator $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ and evaluated the matrix elements in the subspace of tip and substrate under the assumption that all single-particle states $\hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu}$ and $\hat{b}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu'}$ are mutually orthogonal. The matrix elements are then either +1 or −1 depending on the order of the fermionic operators. Finally,

we realized that the sum over γ is a sum over the complete basis of the nanosystem states with $N + 1$ electrons.

The second half of the sum over the intermediate states $|v\rangle$, which involves the intermediate states with an extra hole in the adatom, can be analogously transformed to a similar form,

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_v^{(2)} \frac{\langle f_+ | \hat{\mathcal{V}} | v \rangle \langle v | \hat{\mathcal{V}} | \chi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{\mathcal{E}_v - \mathcal{E}_{N\alpha}} = \\
\sum_\gamma \frac{\langle \chi_{N\beta} | \hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \hat{b}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu'} \hat{\mathcal{V}} \hat{b}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger | \chi_{N-1,\gamma} \rangle \langle \chi_{N-1,\gamma} | \hat{b}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu'} \hat{\mathcal{V}} | \chi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{E_{N-1,\gamma} - E_{N\alpha} + \epsilon_{k'}} = \\
- A_{ki\Gamma}^* B_{k'i'\Gamma'} \sum_\gamma \frac{\langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger | \psi_{N-1,\gamma} \rangle \langle \psi_{N-1,\gamma} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{E_{N-1,\gamma} - E_{N\alpha} + \epsilon_{k'}} = \\
- A_{ki\Gamma}^* B_{k'i'\Gamma'} \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} + \epsilon_{k'}} \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle. \quad (\text{S4})
\end{aligned}$$

Substituting the above two partial expressions to Eq. (2) yields a formula for the positive tunneling current,

$$\begin{aligned}
I_+^{(\alpha)} = \frac{2\pi e}{\hbar} \sum_{\substack{\beta k k' i i' \Gamma \Gamma' \mu \mu' \\ \epsilon_k < \epsilon_F + eV \text{ and } \epsilon_{k'} > \epsilon_F}} |A_{ki\Gamma} B_{k'i'\Gamma'}|^2 \left| \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon_k} \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right. \\
\left. - \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} + \epsilon_{k'}} \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right|^2 \delta(\Delta_{\beta\alpha} - \epsilon_k + \epsilon_{k'}), \quad (\text{S5})
\end{aligned}$$

where the sum runs over all parameters of the final state $|f_+\rangle$ and where a difference (the excitation energy) $\Delta_{\beta\alpha} = E_{N\beta} - E_{N\alpha}$ was introduced. If the k dependence of the tunneling amplitudes A and B can be neglected, the only remaining dependence on k and k' is through the corresponding single-particle energies and hence these sums can be rewritten as integrals weighted with the density of states in the tip, $\rho^t(\epsilon)$, and in the surface, $\rho^s(\epsilon')$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_+^{(\alpha)} = \frac{2\pi e}{\hbar} \sum_{\beta i i' \Gamma \Gamma' \mu \mu'} |A_{i\Gamma} B_{i'\Gamma'}|^2 \int_{-\infty}^{eV} d\epsilon \rho_{i\Gamma}^t(\epsilon) \int_0^\infty d\epsilon' \rho_{i'\Gamma'}^s(\epsilon') \delta(\Delta_{\beta\alpha} - \epsilon + \epsilon') \\
\times \left| \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon} \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right. \\
\left. - \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} + \epsilon'} \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right|^2. \quad (\text{S6})
\end{aligned}$$

In this formula, we make ϵ_F the reference energy and set $\epsilon_F = 0$. Since the voltage V enters only in the upper limit of the integral over ϵ , it is now straightforward to evaluate the differential conductance, $g_+^{(\alpha)} = dI_+^{(\alpha)}/dV$, which yields

$$g_+^{(\alpha)} = \frac{2\pi e^2}{\hbar} \sum_{\beta ii'\Gamma'\mu\mu'} |A_{i\Gamma} B_{i'\Gamma'}|^2 \rho_{i\Gamma}^t(eV) \int_0^\infty d\epsilon' \rho_{i'\Gamma'}^s(\epsilon') \delta(\Delta_{\beta\alpha} - eV + \epsilon') \\ \times \left| \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - eV} \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right. \\ \left. - \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} + \epsilon'} \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right|^2. \quad (\text{S7})$$

Finally, the integral over ϵ' contributes only if $\Delta_{\beta\alpha} - eV < 0$ and hence we arrive at the expression

$$g_+^{(\alpha)} = \frac{2\pi e^2}{\hbar} \sum_{\substack{\beta \\ \Delta_{\beta\alpha} < eV}} \sum_{ii'\Gamma'\mu\mu'} |A_{i\Gamma} B_{i'\Gamma'}|^2 \rho_{i\Gamma}^t(eV) \rho_{i'\Gamma'}^s(eV - \Delta_{\beta\alpha}) \\ \times \left| \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - eV} \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right. \\ \left. - \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\beta} + eV} \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right|^2. \quad (\text{S8})$$

To allow for a more compact presentation, we introduce a transition operator

$$\hat{\mathcal{O}}_{i\Gamma\mu i'\Gamma'\mu'}^{\alpha\beta} = \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - eV} \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger - \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu}^\dagger \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\beta} + eV} \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}, \quad (\text{3c})$$

with the help of which the differential conductance becomes

$$g_+^{(\alpha)} = \frac{2\pi e^2}{\hbar} \sum_{\substack{\beta \\ \Delta_{\beta\alpha} < eV}} \sum_{ii'\Gamma'\mu\mu'} |A_{i\Gamma} B_{i'\Gamma'}|^2 \rho_{i\Gamma}^t(eV) \rho_{i'\Gamma'}^s(eV - \Delta_{\beta\alpha}) \\ \times \left| \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{\mathcal{O}}_{i\Gamma\mu i'\Gamma'\mu'}^{\alpha\beta} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right|^2. \quad (\text{S9})$$

The color boxes in Eq. (3c) mark the two cotunneling channels shown in Fig. S1.

S2.2 Negative current

The derivation of a formula for the negative current and the corresponding differential conductance follows the same steps as the derivation of the positive current.

The two parts of the sum over the intermediate states in Eq. (2) read as

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_v^{(1)} \frac{\langle f_- | \hat{\mathcal{V}} | v \rangle \langle v | \hat{\mathcal{V}} | \chi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{\mathcal{E}_v - \mathcal{E}_{N\alpha}} &= \\
\sum_\gamma \frac{\langle \chi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger \hat{a}_{ki\Gamma\mu} \hat{\mathcal{V}} \hat{b}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu'} | \chi_{N+1,\gamma} \rangle \langle \chi_{N+1,\gamma} | \hat{d}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger \hat{\mathcal{V}} | \chi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{E_{N+1,\gamma} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon_k} &= \\
A_{ki\Gamma} B_{k'i'\Gamma'}^* \sum_\gamma \frac{\langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} | \psi_{N+1,\gamma} \rangle \langle \psi_{N+1,\gamma} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{E_{N+1,\gamma} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon_{k'}} &= \\
A_{ki\Gamma} B_{k'i'\Gamma'}^* \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon_{k'}} \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle & \quad (\text{S10})
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_v^{(2)} \frac{\langle f_- | \hat{\mathcal{V}} | i \rangle \langle i | \hat{\mathcal{V}} | \chi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{\mathcal{E}_v - \mathcal{E}_{N\alpha}} &= \\
\sum_\gamma \frac{\langle \chi_{N\beta} | \hat{s}_{k'i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger \hat{t}_{ki\Gamma\mu} \hat{\mathcal{V}} \hat{t}_{ki\Gamma\mu}^\dagger | \chi_{N-1,\gamma} \rangle \langle \chi_{N-1,\gamma} | \hat{t}_{ki\Gamma\mu} \hat{\mathcal{V}} | \chi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{E_{N-1,\gamma} - E_{N\alpha} + \epsilon_k} &= \\
- B_{k'i'\Gamma'}^* A_{ki\Gamma} \sum_\gamma \frac{\langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger | \psi_{N-1,\gamma} \rangle \langle \psi_{N-1,\gamma} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{E_{N-1,\gamma} - E_{N\alpha} + \epsilon_k} &= \\
- B_{k'i'\Gamma'}^* A_{ki\Gamma} \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} + \epsilon_k} \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle. & \quad (\text{S11})
\end{aligned}$$

Inserting these two expressions into Eq. (2) we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned}
I_-^{(\alpha)} &= -\frac{2\pi e}{\hbar} \sum_{\substack{\beta k k' i' \Gamma' \mu \mu' \\ \epsilon_k > \epsilon_F + eV \text{ and } \epsilon_{k'} < \epsilon_F}} |A_{ki\Gamma} B_{k'i'\Gamma'}^*|^2 \left| \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon_{k'}} \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} + \epsilon_k} \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right|^2 \delta(\Delta_{\beta\alpha} + \epsilon_k - \epsilon_{k'}). \quad (\text{S12})
\end{aligned}$$

The subsequent neglect of the k dependence of the amplitudes A and B , the replacement of the momentum sums with integrals over the single-particle energies,

and setting $\epsilon_F = 0$ yields

$$I_-^{(\alpha)} = -\frac{2\pi e}{\hbar} \sum_{\beta ii'\Gamma'\mu\mu'} |A_{i\Gamma} B_{i'\Gamma'}|^2 \int_{eV}^{\infty} d\epsilon \rho_{i\Gamma}^t(\epsilon) \int_{-\infty}^0 d\epsilon' \rho_{i'\Gamma'}^s(\epsilon') \delta(\Delta_{\beta\alpha} + \epsilon - \epsilon') \\ \times \left| \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon'} \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right. \\ \left. - \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} + \epsilon} \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right|^2. \quad (\text{S13})$$

Then, the differential conductance $g_-^{(\alpha)} = dI_-^{(\alpha)}/dV$ becomes

$$g_-^{(\alpha)} = \frac{2\pi e^2}{\hbar} \sum_{\beta ii'\Gamma'\mu\mu'} |A_{i\Gamma} B_{i'\Gamma'}|^2 \rho_{i\Gamma}^t(eV) \int_{-\infty}^0 d\epsilon' \rho_{i'\Gamma'}^s(\epsilon') \delta(\Delta_{\beta\alpha} + eV - \epsilon') \\ \times \left| \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon'} \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right. \\ \left. - \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} + eV} \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right|^2. \quad (\text{S14})$$

The remaining integral contributes only if $\Delta_{\beta\alpha} + eV < 0$. With this observation we finally come to

$$g_-^{(\alpha)} = \frac{2\pi e^2}{\hbar} \sum_{\substack{\beta \\ \Delta_{\beta\alpha} < -eV}} \sum_{ii'\Gamma'\mu\mu'} |A_{i\Gamma} B_{i'\Gamma'}|^2 \rho_{i\Gamma}^t(eV) \rho_{i'\Gamma'}^s(eV + \Delta_{\beta\alpha}) \\ \times \left| \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\beta} - eV} \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right. \\ \left. - \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{d}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^\dagger \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} + eV} \hat{d}_{i\Gamma\mu} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right|^2. \quad (\text{S15})$$

In terms of the transition operator $\hat{\mathcal{O}}$ defined in Eq. (3c), the expression becomes

$$g_-^{(\alpha)} = \frac{2\pi e^2}{\hbar} \sum_{\substack{\beta \\ \Delta_{\beta\alpha} < -eV}} \sum_{ii'\Gamma'\mu\mu'} |A_{i\Gamma} B_{i'\Gamma'}|^2 \rho_{i\Gamma}^t(eV) \rho_{i'\Gamma'}^s(eV + \Delta_{\beta\alpha}) \\ \times \left| \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{\mathcal{O}}_{i'\Gamma'\mu' i\Gamma\mu}^{\beta\alpha} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right|^2. \quad (\text{S16})$$

S2.3 Relation between the negative and positive currents

Our final equations for the differential conductances, Eqs. (S9) and (S16), are very similar but not exactly the same. We can observe that the matrix element of the

Figure S2: Top (left) and side view (right) of the Fe/Cu(100) unit cell as used in the DFT calculations. The iron atom is adsorbed on both sides of the slab to maintain as high symmetry as possible (including inversion). The figure was made with VESTA [1].

transition operator as it appears in Eq. (S9) can be transformed as

$$|\langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{O}_{i\Gamma\mu}^{\alpha\beta} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle|^2 = |\langle \psi_{N\alpha} | [\hat{O}_{i\Gamma\mu}^{\alpha\beta}]^\dagger | \psi_{N\beta} \rangle|^2 = |\langle \psi_{N\alpha} | \hat{O}_{i'\Gamma'\mu'}^{\alpha\beta} | \psi_{N\beta} \rangle|^2, \quad (\text{S17})$$

which is the corresponding expression from Eq. (S16) with α and β interchanged. If we denote the whole summand of Eq. (S9) as

$$\mathcal{G}_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{2\pi e^2}{\hbar} \sum_{ii'\Gamma'\mu\mu'} |A_{i\Gamma} B_{i'\Gamma'}|^2 \rho_{i\Gamma}^t(eV) \rho_{i'\Gamma'}^s(eV - \Delta_{\beta\alpha}) |\langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{O}_{i\Gamma\mu}^{\alpha\beta} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle|^2, \quad (3b)$$

then the expressions for the differential conductances become

$$g_+^{(\alpha)} = \sum_{\beta} \mathcal{G}_{\alpha\beta} \quad \text{and} \quad g_-^{(\alpha)} = \sum_{\beta} \mathcal{G}_{\beta\alpha}. \quad (\text{S18})$$

S3 Fe adatom on Cu(100) probed by Nc-terminated tip

S3.1 DFT calculations of Fe adatom on Cu(100) surface

We have employed the density-functional theory (DFT) to estimate the electronic structure of the iron adatom on the Cu(100) surface. Our calculations were done with the WIEN2K package [2] that implements the linearized augmented plane-wave method and its extensions, and combines a scalar-relativistic description with

Figure S3: Orbital-resolved density of states in the 3d shell of the Fe adatom (a calculation without spin-orbit coupling). Majority spin is shown as positive values, minority spin as negative values.

spin-orbit coupling. We used the spin-polarized generalized-gradient approximation (PBE-GGA) for the exchange-correlation functional [3].

We modeled the surface as a slab consisting of seven Cu layers. The horizontal dimensions of the unit cell were $7.668 \text{ \AA} \times 7.668 \text{ \AA}$, corresponding to the experimental lattice constant of fcc Cu $a = 3.615 \text{ \AA}$. The periodic repetitions of the slab in the vertical direction were separated by 10.58 \AA ($20 a_B$) of vacuum. The Fe adatom was placed in the hollow position (C_{4v} symmetry) on both sides of the slab such that the unit cell was symmetric with respect to the inversion (Fig. S2). The orientation of the coordinate system is such that the in-plane 3d orbitals centered at the adatom behave as follows: xy points to the nearest neighbors and $x^2 - y^2$ points to the voids between the nearest neighbors. All internal coordinates in the simulation cell were relaxed until the forces acting on the individual atoms became smaller than $1 \text{ mRy}/a_B$. During the relaxation, the spin-orbit coupling was switched off. The optimal adatom distance above the surface was found to be 1.56 \AA .

The parameters determining the accuracy of the DFT calculations were: the radii of the muffin-tin spheres were $R_{\text{MT}} = 2.07 a_B$, the basis-set cutoff K_{max} was defined with $R_{\text{MT}} \times K_{\text{max}} = 8.0$, and the Brillouin zone was sampled on a k -point mesh $10 \times 10 \times 1$. The default WIEN2K basis set with local orbitals for semicore states Fe 3p and Cu 3p was used.

The calculations give the spin moment at the Fe adatom as 1.5 (determined by integration of the spin density in the Fe muffin-tin sphere, which may slightly underestimate the spin moment) or as approximately 1.6 (determined as a half of the spin moment of the whole unit cell, which counts also the small spin moments induced at neighboring Cu atoms), which agrees with previous DFT calculations

[4–6]. The density of states projected on the adatom 3d orbitals is plotted Fig. S3, indicating that the three unpaired electrons reside in the z^2 and $x^2 - y^2$ orbitals, and in one of the doubly degenerate xz and yz orbitals.

After switching on the spin-orbit coupling, the magnetic anisotropy energy (MAE) can be estimated as a difference between the total energies of the states with magnetic moments oriented in plane, [100] direction, and out of plane, [001] direction. This way we obtain $\Delta_{\text{MAE}} = E_{[100]} - E_{[001]} \approx 0.6$ meV/Fe, the sign of which is consistent with experiments (the spin is out of plane in the ground state) but the magnitude is an order of magnitude too small (if our understanding of the inelastic tunneling spectra, detailed in Appendix A, is correct). Lazarovits *et al.* [4] reported a larger value (2.9 meV/Fe) using a different DFT implementation (KKR-ASA, VWN-LDA for the exchange-correlation functional [7], and the magnetic force theorem for the estimation of the magnetic anisotropy energy) but even that is too small to be consistent with the inelastic tunneling spectra. We do not consider the underestimated magnitude of Δ_{MAE} as a critical contradiction, however, since DFT does not necessarily have the precision to determine such small energy differences accurately, and we did not check the convergence of Δ_{MAE} with respect to all parameters, namely with respect to the size of the supercell, which is computationally very costly and out of scope of the present study. We only verified that Δ_{MAE} stays essentially the same when the k -point mesh is increased to $15 \times 15 \times 1$. In any case, the model calculations we present in our paper do not rely on the DFT estimate of the magnetic anisotropy. We only use DFT to identify the occupation of the individual Fe 3d orbitals, which should be a much more robust quantity than the magnetic anisotropy energy.

S3.2 Spin model for coupled Ni and Fe spins

The anisotropic two-spin model for the coupled Ni and Fe spins,

$$\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{\text{spin}} = D_{\text{Ni}} \hat{S}_{z,\text{Ni}}^2 + D_{\text{Fe}} \hat{S}_{z,\text{Fe}}^2 - J \hat{\mathbf{S}}_{\text{Ni}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{S}}_{\text{Fe}}, \quad (6)$$

allows for an analytic solution, which we used when plotting Figs. 2 and 5. The Hamiltonian $\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{\text{spin}}$ commutes with the z component of the total spin, $\hat{S}_{z,\text{tot}} = \hat{S}_{z,\text{Ni}} + \hat{S}_{z,\text{Fe}}$, and hence the expectation value M_{tot} of $\hat{S}_{z,\text{tot}}$ is a conserved quantity and the eigenstates with $\pm M_{\text{tot}}$ are degenerate. The half of the Hilbert space with positive M_{tot} decomposes into three subspaces: one-dimensional $M_{\text{tot}} = 5/2$, two-dimensional $M_{\text{tot}} = 3/2$ and three-dimensional $M_{\text{tot}} = 1/2$. The eigenenergy for the $M_{\text{tot}} = 5/2$ state is

$$E_2 = \frac{9}{4} D_{\text{Fe}} + D_{\text{Ni}} + \frac{3}{2} J, \quad (\text{S19})$$

Table S2: Eigenstate energies E and the gaps $\Delta = E - E_0$ for the spin model, Eq. (6), expanded in powers of the exchange J with only terms up to J^2 retained (the energy of state 2 is exact as shown). The energy increases from bottom to top when $|D_{\text{Fe}}| \gg D_{\text{Ni}}$, the color coding corresponds to Figs. 2 and 5-7 in the main text. The z projection of the total spin M_{tot} and of the spins at the Ni and Fe atoms, M_{Ni} and M_{Fe} , are listed as well; M_{tot} is a conserving quantity (quantum number) since the model is axially symmetric around z , whereas M_{Ni} and M_{Fe} have the values as shown only at $J = 0$.

state	M_{Ni}	M_{Fe}	M_{tot}	E	Δ
5	± 1	$\pm \frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{3}{2} \pm \frac{3}{2}$	$\frac{1}{4}D_{\text{Fe}} + D_{\text{Ni}} + \frac{1}{2}J + \frac{3}{2D_{\text{Ni}} - 4D_{\text{Fe}}}J^2$	$-2D_{\text{Fe}} + D_{\text{Ni}} + \frac{1}{2}J + \frac{3}{D_{\text{Ni}} - 2D_{\text{Fe}}}J^2$
4	± 1	$\pm \frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2} \pm \frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{4}D_{\text{Fe}} + D_{\text{Ni}} - \frac{1}{2}J + \frac{2}{D_{\text{Ni}}}J^2$	$-2D_{\text{Fe}} + D_{\text{Ni}} - \frac{1}{2}J + \left(\frac{2}{D_{\text{Ni}}} + \frac{3}{2D_{\text{Ni}} - 4D_{\text{Fe}}}\right)J^2$
3	0	$\pm \frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2} \pm \frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{4}D_{\text{Fe}} - \left(\frac{2}{D_{\text{Ni}}} - \frac{3}{2D_{\text{Ni}} + 4D_{\text{Fe}}}\right)J^2$	$-2D_{\text{Fe}} - \left(\frac{2}{D_{\text{Ni}}} + \frac{6D_{\text{Fe}}}{(D_{\text{Ni}} + 2D_{\text{Fe}})(D_{\text{Ni}} - 2D_{\text{Fe}})}\right)J^2$
2	± 1	$\pm \frac{3}{2}$	$\frac{5}{2} \pm \frac{5}{2}$	$\frac{9}{4}D_{\text{Fe}} + D_{\text{Ni}} + \frac{3}{2}J$	$D_{\text{Ni}} + \frac{3}{2}J + \frac{3}{2D_{\text{Ni}} - 4D_{\text{Fe}}}J^2$
1	± 1	$\pm \frac{3}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2} \pm \frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{9}{4}D_{\text{Fe}} + D_{\text{Ni}} - \frac{3}{2}J + \frac{3}{2D_{\text{Ni}} + 4D_{\text{Fe}}}J^2$	$D_{\text{Ni}} - \frac{3}{2}J + \frac{3D_{\text{Ni}}}{(D_{\text{Ni}} + 2D_{\text{Fe}})(D_{\text{Ni}} - 2D_{\text{Fe}})}J^2$
0	0	$\pm \frac{3}{2}$	$\frac{3}{2} \pm \frac{3}{2}$	$\frac{9}{4}D_{\text{Fe}} - \frac{3}{2D_{\text{Ni}} - 4D_{\text{Fe}}}J^2$	0

the eigenenergies in the $M_{\text{tot}} = 3/2$ subspace are

$$E_{0,5} = \frac{5D_{\text{Fe}}}{4} + \frac{D_{\text{Ni}}}{2} + \frac{J}{4} \mp \frac{D_{\text{Ni}} - 2D_{\text{Fe}}}{2} \sqrt{1 + \frac{J}{D_{\text{Ni}} - 2D_{\text{Fe}}} + \frac{25}{4} \left(\frac{J}{D_{\text{Ni}} - 2D_{\text{Fe}}} \right)^2}, \quad (\text{S20})$$

and the eigenenergies in the $M_{\text{tot}} = 1/2$ subspace are roots of a cubic equation that do not have a compact enough form to be written here explicitly. Instead, we list all eigenstate energies expanded in powers of the exchange J up to the second order in Table S2.

If the exchange term $J\hat{\mathbf{S}}_{\text{Ni}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{S}}_{\text{Fe}}$ is simplified to the Ising form $J\hat{S}_{z,\text{Ni}}\hat{S}_{z,\text{Fe}}$, the Hamiltonian $\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{\text{spin}}$ commutes with the z projections of the individual spins, $\hat{S}_{z,\text{Ni}}$ and $\hat{S}_{z,\text{Fe}}$. This makes the eigenvalue problem trivial and the exact eigenvalues are given by the expressions from Table S2 with the J^2 terms dropped [6].

S4 Comparison to Delgado and Fernández-Rossier [8]

Our derivation of the differential conductance described in Sec. S2 is based on assumptions that are very similar to those of Delgado and Fernández-Rossier in [8], except that their theory is more general, since it is applicable also at non-zero temperatures and is not limited to small tunneling currents. After a closer inspection, however, we found that their theory does not reduce to ours in the limit of zero temperature and small currents. The origin of the discrepancies is a slightly different operator describing the tunneling between the nanosystem and the electrodes. The tunneling operator employed in [8] has the form

$$\hat{\mathcal{V}} = \sum_{kim\sigma} \left(A_{kim\sigma} \hat{a}_{k\sigma}^\dagger \hat{d}_{im\sigma} + A_{kim\sigma}^* \hat{d}_{im\sigma}^\dagger \hat{a}_{k\sigma} + B_{kim\sigma} \hat{b}_{k\sigma}^\dagger \hat{d}_{im\sigma} + B_{kim\sigma}^* \hat{d}_{im\sigma}^\dagger \hat{b}_{k\sigma} \right), \quad (\text{S21})$$

which differs from our Eq. (1) by coupling the magnetic centers directly to the Bloch waves in the electrodes instead of the symmetry-conserving waves.

We now retrace the main steps of our derivation (Sec. S2) for the tunneling operator $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ given by Eq. (S21). The sums over the intermediate states $|v\rangle$ slightly

change, we explicitly show only the analogon of Eq. (S3),

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_v^{(1)} \frac{\langle f_+ | \hat{\mathcal{V}} | v \rangle \langle v | \hat{\mathcal{V}} | \chi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{\mathcal{E}_v - \mathcal{E}_{N\alpha}} &= \\
&\sum_\gamma \frac{\langle \chi_{N\beta} | \hat{a}_{k\sigma}^\dagger \hat{b}_{k'\sigma'} \hat{\mathcal{V}} \hat{a}_{k\sigma} | \chi_{N+1,\gamma} \rangle \langle \chi_{N+1,\gamma} | \hat{a}_{k\sigma}^\dagger \hat{\mathcal{V}} | \chi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{E_{N+1,\gamma} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon_k} = \\
&\sum_\gamma \frac{\langle \psi_{N\beta} | (\sum_{i'm'} B_{k'i'm'\sigma'} \hat{d}_{i'm'\sigma'}) | \psi_{N+1,\gamma} \rangle \langle \psi_{N+1,\gamma} | (\sum_{im} A_{kim\sigma}^* \hat{d}_{im\sigma}^\dagger) | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle}{E_{N+1,\gamma} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon_k} = \\
&\langle \psi_{N\beta} | \underbrace{\left(\sum_{i'm'} B_{k'i'm'\sigma'} \hat{d}_{i'm'\sigma'} \right)}_{\hat{B}_{k'\sigma'}} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon_k} \underbrace{\left(\sum_{im} A_{kim\sigma}^* \hat{d}_{im\sigma}^\dagger \right)}_{\hat{A}_{k\sigma}^\dagger} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle. \quad (\text{S22})
\end{aligned}$$

Because the tip and surface states coupled to the nanosystem do not depend on indexes i and m now, the sums over these orbital degrees of freedom originating from the tunneling operator $\hat{\mathcal{V}}$ survive inside the matrix element $\langle \psi_{N\beta} | \bullet | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle$.

The formula for the positive current, Eq. (S5), changes to

$$\begin{aligned}
I_+^{(\alpha)} &= \frac{2\pi e}{\hbar} \sum_{\beta k k' \sigma \sigma'} \left| \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{B}_{k'\sigma'} \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - \epsilon_k} \hat{A}_{k\sigma}^\dagger | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{A}_{k\sigma}^\dagger \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} + \epsilon_{k'}} \hat{B}_{k'\sigma'} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle \right|^2 \delta(\Delta_{\beta\alpha} - \epsilon_k + \epsilon_{k'}), \quad (\text{S23})
\end{aligned}$$

where the outer sum, that is, the sum over the final states $|f_+\rangle$, now does not involve the orbital degrees of freedom i and m , since the final state does not depend on them. When the k dependence of the tunneling amplitudes A and B is neglected, which we do in Sec. S2 and Delgado and Fernández-Rossier do in [8], the differential conductance takes the form

$$g_+^{(\alpha)} = \frac{2\pi e^2}{\hbar} \sum_{\beta} \sum_{\sigma \sigma'}^{\Delta_{\beta\alpha} < eV} \rho^t(eV) \rho^s(eV - \Delta_{\beta\alpha}) |\langle \psi_{N\beta} | \hat{\mathcal{O}}_{\sigma\sigma'}^{\alpha\beta} | \psi_{N\alpha} \rangle|^2, \quad (\text{S24})$$

where the transition operator is

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\mathcal{O}}_{\sigma\sigma'}^{\alpha\beta} &= \left(\sum_{i'm'} B_{i'm'\sigma'} \hat{d}_{i'm'\sigma'} \right) \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\alpha} - eV} \left(\sum_{im} A_{im\sigma}^* \hat{d}_{im\sigma}^\dagger \right) \\
&\quad - \left(\sum_{im} A_{im\sigma}^* \hat{d}_{im\sigma}^\dagger \right) \frac{1}{\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} - E_{N\beta} + eV} \left(\sum_{i'm'} B_{i'm'\sigma'} \hat{d}_{i'm'\sigma'} \right). \quad (\text{S25})
\end{aligned}$$

Figure S4: Comparison of the d^2I/dV^2 spectra calculated with our tunneling Hamiltonian, Eq. (1), (left) and with the tunneling Hamiltonian of Delgado and Fernández-Rossier [8], Eq. (S21), (right). The system is Fe adatom on the Cu(100) surface probed by a nickelocene terminated tip, the parameters of the atomic shells are listed in rows A and C in Table I (the same $\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns}$ as in Fig. 6). The spectra are normalized to the largest peak independently at each t . The experimental data measured at tip-adatom distances $z = 80$ pm and $z = 133$ pm are included for comparison [6].

The last two equations have the same structure as the equations listed in Appendix B of [8]. Note that i denotes *all* orbital degrees of freedom in [8], not just the site.

We have implemented these equations and applied them to the same cases that are discussed in the main text. Figure S4 shows the calculated d^2I/dV^2 spectra corresponding to a Fe adatom on the Cu(100) surface probed by a nickelocene-decorated tip. The differences between the tunneling Hamiltonian from [8], Eq. (S21), and our tunneling Hamiltonian, Eq. (1), are not dramatic, but they are certainly visible – and the match to the experimental d^2I/dV^2 spectra [6] is distinctly worse with the Hamiltonian employed in [8].

In the case of a partially filled atomic shell placed in a homogeneous magnetic field \mathbf{B} , the nanosystem Hamiltonian is just

$$\hat{\mathcal{H}}_{ns} = \sum_{mm'\sigma\sigma'} [\zeta(\ell \cdot \mathbf{s}) - \mu_B(\ell + 2\mathbf{s}) \cdot \mathbf{B}]_{\sigma\sigma'}^{mm'} \hat{d}_{m\sigma}^\dagger \hat{d}_{m'\sigma'} + \hat{U}. \quad (\text{S26})$$

When the nanosystem–electrode tunneling amplitudes are taken in the simple form $A_{m\sigma} = A$ and $B_{m\sigma} = B$, the system should be entirely isotropic with the only

direction-dependent term being the interaction with the magnetic field. Yet, the tunneling Hamiltonian from [8] yields *different* d^2I/dV^2 spectra for different directions of the magnetic field (say along z and along x), which is clearly *inconsistent* with the symmetry of the system. Our tunneling Hamiltonian, Eq. (1), on the other hand, gives d^2I/dV^2 spectra independent of the direction of the magnetic field. The different outcomes of the two tunneling Hamiltonians can be traced to the property that the tunneling events described by Eq. (1) conserve spin as well as orbital moment, the tunneling described by Eq. (S21) conserves only spin.

The spurious directional dependence can be analytically illustrated on the d shell hosting one spinless electron discussed in Appendix B. To keep things as simple as possible, we consider the limit $U \rightarrow \infty$, which makes the two-electron intermediate states inaccessible and the tunneling can proceed only via the empty shell. Our transition operator, Eq. (B1), then simplifies to $\hat{O}_{mm'}^{\alpha\beta} = \epsilon^{-1} \hat{d}_m^\dagger \hat{d}_{m'}$, and the differential conductance (positive current) is given by

$$g_+^{(\alpha)} \sim \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} \sum_{\substack{\beta \\ \Delta_{\beta\alpha} < eV}} \sum_{mm'} |\langle \beta | \hat{d}_m^\dagger \hat{d}_{m'} | \alpha \rangle|^2 \equiv \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} \sum_{\substack{\beta \\ \Delta_{\beta\alpha} < eV}} \sum_{mm'} |\langle \beta | \hat{d}_m^\dagger | 0 \rangle \langle 0 | \hat{d}_{m'} | \alpha \rangle|^2 =$$

$$\frac{1}{\epsilon^2} \sum_{\substack{\beta \\ \Delta_{\beta\alpha} < eV}} \underbrace{\left(\sum_m |\langle \beta | \hat{d}_m^\dagger | 0 \rangle|^2 \right)}_{=1} \underbrace{\left(\sum_{m'} |\langle 0 | \hat{d}_{m'} | \alpha \rangle|^2 \right)}_{=1} = \sum_{\substack{\beta \\ \Delta_{\beta\alpha} < eV}} \frac{1}{\epsilon^2}, \quad (\text{S27})$$

where operators \hat{d}_m correspond to eigenstates of the z component of the orbital moment \hat{l}_z , and $|\alpha\rangle$ and $|\beta\rangle$ are one-electron eigenstates of the shell Hamiltonian. The sums over m and m' in the second line are just normalization conditions of the states $|\alpha\rangle$ and $|\beta\rangle$, since the states \hat{d}_m form a basis of the shell. The final expression for the differential conductance does not depend on any details of the eigenstates, and hence it is invariant with respect to the direction of the magnetic field applied to the shell.

The alternative transition operator, Eq. (S25), has the form

$$\hat{O}^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\sum_m A^* \hat{d}_m^\dagger \right) \left(\sum_{m'} B \hat{d}_{m'} \right) \equiv \frac{1}{\epsilon} \left(\sum_m A^* \hat{d}_m^\dagger \right) |0\rangle \langle 0| \left(\sum_{m'} B \hat{d}_{m'} \right), \quad (\text{S28})$$

and the corresponding formula for the differential conductance, Eq. (S24), reads as

$$g_+^{(\alpha)} \sim \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} \sum_{\substack{\beta \\ \Delta_{\beta\alpha} < eV}} \left| \langle \beta | \left(\sum_m \hat{d}_m^\dagger \right) | 0 \rangle \langle 0 | \left(\sum_{m'} \hat{d}_{m'} \right) | \alpha \rangle \right|^2. \quad (\text{S29})$$

When the magnetic field is oriented along the z direction, the eigenstates of the

shell are simply $|\beta\rangle = \hat{d}_\beta^\dagger|0\rangle$ and the differential conductance again becomes

$$g_+^{(\alpha)} \sim \sum_{\substack{\beta \\ \Delta_{\beta\alpha} < eV}} \frac{1}{\epsilon^2}, \quad (\text{S30})$$

since only one term from each of the sums over m and m' contributes. When the magnetic field is oriented along the x direction, the eigenstates of the shell can be obtained by rotating the B_z eigenstates by $-\pi/2$ around the y axis (this rotation transforms the z axis to the x axis), namely $|\tilde{\beta}\rangle = \exp(-i\pi \hat{l}_y/2) \hat{d}_\beta^\dagger|0\rangle$. The differential conductance, Eq. (S29), then transforms to

$$g_+^{(\alpha)} \sim \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} \sum_{\substack{\beta \\ \Delta_{\beta\alpha} < eV}} \left| \sum_m \langle 0 | \hat{d}_\beta e^{i\pi \hat{l}_y/2} \hat{d}_m^\dagger | 0 \rangle \right|^2 \left| \sum_{m'} \langle 0 | \hat{d}_{m'} e^{-i\pi \hat{l}_y/2} \hat{d}_\alpha^\dagger | 0 \rangle \right|^2 =$$

$$\frac{1}{\epsilon^2} \sum_{\substack{\beta \\ \Delta_{\beta\alpha} < eV}} \left| \sum_m \langle \beta | e^{i\pi \hat{l}_y/2} | m \rangle \right|^2 \left| \sum_{m'} \langle m' | e^{-i\pi \hat{l}_y/2} | \alpha \rangle \right|^2. \quad (\text{S31})$$

It involves modulus squared of sums of columns/rows of the unitary matrix

$$e^{-i\pi \hat{l}_y/2} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{4} & \frac{1}{2} & \sqrt{\frac{3}{8}} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{4} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ \sqrt{\frac{3}{8}} & 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & 0 & \sqrt{\frac{3}{8}} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{4} & -\frac{1}{2} & \sqrt{\frac{3}{8}} & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{4} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{S32})$$

and is clearly different from Eq. (S30). The sums of some rows are zero and the corresponding terms entirely drop from the sum over β in Eq. (S31).

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